

**“A STUDY ON FUND MANAGEMENT BASED ON EQUITY
INVESTMENT OF IIFL”**

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Abstract:

The Indian banking witnessed a paradigm shift in their operations after the financial sector reforms in 1991. These reforms led to the emergence of new banks, new instruments, new methods of doing business, and finally heightened competition in the banking industry. In this context, it is imperative on the part of the Indian banking industry to strengthen financial base, increase overall efficiency, and improve profitability by designing appropriate funds management policies and practices. This research examines the profitability of funds management of the select company In with a cost-benefit perspectives

Keyword: *Mutual fund, Equity Fund, Liquidity, Profitability.*

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Introduction:

IIFL Holding Limited is an Indian Diversified financial services company headquarters in Mumbai. The Organization was found by Nirmal Jain. Its grouped companies are Canadian investor's prem Watsa. The name was later changed to India Infoline Limited. IIFL Holding Limited is an Indian Diversified financial services company headquarters in Mumbai.

IIFL is a ranked among the top seven financial company in India. And top independent financial services firm in India in term of market capitalization. Nirmal Jain is the chairmen of the group and R Venkataraman is the Group managing director and co-promoter. IIFL was founded in October 17, 1995 by Nirmal Jain. IIFL Holdings Ltd, formerly known as India Infoline Limited, and offer services including financial services

group with diverse operating businesses, mainly Non-Banking and Housing Finance, Wealth and Asset Management, Broking, Financial Product Distribution, Investment Banking, Institutional Equities, Realty and Property Advisory Services.

An Equity Fund can be actively managed or passively managed. Index cash and ETFs are passively managed. Equity mutual cash are principally categorised in accordance to company size, the investment style of the holdings in the portfolio and geography. The measurement of an equity fund is determined with the aid of a market capitalization, whilst the funding style, reflected in the fund's stock holdings, is also used to categorize equity mutual funds. An equity fund is a mutual fund scheme that invests predominantly in equity stocks.

In the Indian context, as per current SEBI Mutual Fund Regulations, an equity mutual fund scheme need to make investments at least 65% of the scheme's assets in equities and equity related instruments.

Under the tax regime in India, equity funds revel in certain tax benefits (such as, there is no incidence of lengthy time period capital good points tax on fairness shares or fairness money which are held for at least 12 months from the date of acquisition). As per current Income Tax rules, an "Equity Oriented Fund" means a Mutual Fund Scheme the place the investible funds are invested in equity shares in domestic corporations to the extent of more than 65% of the total proceeds of such fund. An Equity Fund can be actively managed or passively managed. Index cash and ETFs are passively managed. Equity mutual cash are principally categorised in accordance to company size, the investment style of the holdings in the portfolio and geography. The measurement of an equity fund is determined with the aid of a market capitalization, whilst the funding style, reflected in the fund's stock holdings, is also used to categorize equity mutual funds. Equity dollars are additionally categorised by way of whether they are domestic (investing in stocks of only Indian companies) or global (investing in stocks of remote places companies). These can be vast market, regional or single-country funds. Some specialty equity money goal enterprise sectors, such as health care, commodities and real property and are acknowledged as Sectoral Funds.

Investment Carriage:

In many ways, equity funds are perfect investment cars for traders that are now not as well-versed in financial investing or do now not possess a massive quantity of capital with which to invest. Equity money are realistic investments for most people. The

attributes that make equity funds most suitable for small individual investors are the discount of chance resulting from a fund's portfolio diversification and the particularly small quantity of capital required to collect shares of an equity fund. A large quantity of investment capital would be required for a man or woman investor to achieve a similar diploma of chance discount through diversification of a portfolio of direct inventory holdings. Pooling small investors' capital lets in an equity fund to diversify successfully without burdening every investor with large capital requirements. The charge of the equity fund is based on the fund's net asset price (NAV) less its liabilities. A more different fund skill that there is less negative impact of a man or woman stock's unfavourable fee motion on the overall portfolio and on the share fee of the fairness fund. Equity funds are managed with the aid of experienced professional portfolio managers, and their previous overall performance is a count of public record. Transparency and reporting requirements for equity cash are heavily regulated by the federal government.

Review of Literature:

James chames-

An equity fund is a mutual fund that invests principally in stocks. It can be actively or passively (index fund) managed. Equity funds are also known as stock funds.

Meir Statman- (August 5, 2009)

Analysing 1992-2007 returns of stocks rated on social responsibility, this study found that this tilt gave such investors an advantage over conventional investors. The study also found that shunning resulted in a disadvantage for such investors relative to conventional investors. The advantage from tilting toward stocks of companies with high social responsibility scores is largely offset by the disadvantage from the exclusion of stocks of shunned companies. Socially responsible investors can thus do both well and good by adopting the best-in-class method in constructing their portfolios: tilting toward stocks of companies with high scores on social responsibility characteristics but refraining from shunning stocks of any company.

Will Kenton And Chris B Murphy-(June 2018)

Equity is typically referred to as shareholder equity (also known as shareholder equity) which represents the amount of money that would be returned to a company's shareholders if all of the assets were liquidated and all of the company's debt was paid off.

Equity is found on a company's balance sheet and is one of the most common financial

metrics employed by analysts to assess the financial health of a company. Shareholder equity can also represent the book value of a company. Equity can sometimes be offered as payment in kind.

There are various types of equity that extend beyond a corporation's balance sheet. In this article, we'll explore the different types of equity including how investors can calculate a corporation's equity or net worth.

Will Kenton- (Jun 29, 2018)

Funds management is the overseeing and handling of a financial institution's cash flow. The fund manager ensures that the maturity schedules of the deposits coincide with the demand for loans. To do this, the manager looks at both the liabilities and the assets that influence the bank's ability to issue credit.

Funds management – also referred to as asset management – covers any kind of system that maintains the value of an entity. It may be applied to intangible assets (e.g., intellectual property and goodwill), and tangible assets (e.g., equipment and real estate). It is the systematic process of operating, deploying, maintaining, disposing, and upgrading assets in the most cost-efficient and profit-yielding way possible.

A fund manager must pay close attention to cost and risk to capitalize on the cash flow opportunities. A financial institution runs on the ability to offer credit to customers. Ensuring the proper liquidity of the funds is a crucial aspect of the fund manager's position. Funds management can also refer to the management of fund assets.

In the financial world, the term "fund management" describes people and institutions that manage investments on behalf of investors. An example would be investment managers who fix the assets of pension funds for pension investors.

R. Sreepriya, P. Gurusamy- (2013)

Additional income or growth in value can be achieved by investment. Waiting for rewards is the main characteristic of investment. Investment is allocation monetary resources to get returns over given period. Surplus funds are invested with different channels by salaried class people. This research analyses the different investment avenues. 81 percent respondents faced problem at the time of investment.

V. R. Palanivelu, K. Chandrakumar (2013)

This study divides the investment in different categories like Equity with high rate of return and risk , Debts with fixed interest rate on investments, Fixed deposits with bank , insurance , public provident fund low rate of return on investment and secured. Data

analyses reveals that 40percent respondents like to invest in insurance, 30 percent respondents like to invest in bank deposits, 18 percent like to invest in Gold and real estate.

Varsha Virani (2013)

Investment plans are important to meet consequences in future, to meet financial goals. Economic development is boosted with the help of investments. Investment in Bank helps in circulation of funds for nation's development. Financial independence, increase in wealth, and personal goals can be achieved through investments. Investment avenues are divided into high risk and low risk instruments.

B. N. Panda, J. K. Panda (2012)

The study analyses the difference in perception of investors in decision of investing on the basis of age and gender. Various investment options are examined in these research such as Secured deposits, Life insurance policies, Provident fund , Pension schemes, Bonds, Debentures, Equity shares, Mutual funds, Real estate, postal schemes etc. investment decisions are to be taken by self and has to wait to see the results of it, which fascinates some investors.

N. Srividhya, S. Visalakshi (2013)

The study analyses various avenues of investment such as Government deposits, bonds, real estates, post office saving certificates life insurance policies, mutual funds etc. study covers Government colleges, Private colleges and aided colleges which states that maximum teachers saves below one lakh. Maximum respondents invest in fixed deposits.

Rajeshwari Jain (2014)

Investment is the consumption and saving opportunity in future expressed in monetary terms. Two classes of investments like Fixed income statements i.e. Preference shares, Bonds, fixed deposits and Variable income investment i.e. equality capital, proprietary ownership. Data shows that respondents between the age group of 26 years to 35 years are involve in investment activities.

Ravi Vyas (2012)

This study finds the form of investments preferred by investors. Mutual fund investment is a secured investment with good returns on investments. Data analyses show that maximum respondent invest in Gold followed by bank deposits and Insurance schemes. Mutual fund investments are very limited. For Safety, Liquidity, Reliability, Tax benefits and high returns Mutual fund has average score among investors.

Priyanka Jain (2012)

The study analyses the various investment avenues available for the investors. It states Equity shares has low return but high capital appreciation, risk liquidity, Marketability, tax benefit, Debentures has high return but low risk liquidity and marketability. Bank deposits have moderate returns but low capital appreciation and risk liquidity.

Dr.S.Suriyamurthi (2012)

This study deals with the behavior of the investor to identify the better investment avenues available in India. The investment strategy is a plan, which is created to guide an investor to choose the most appropriate investment portfolio that will help them to achieve their financial goals within a particular period of time. By increasing personal wealth, investing can contribute to higher, overall economic growth and prosperity. The process of investing helps companies where they can raise their capital through financial markets. Specific types of investments provide other benefits for the investor, corporate as well as the society. The Indian investors are very much aware about the concept of portfolio allotments and risk and return of the investment. The mantra of the investment is „Prevention is better than Cure” which is expected with more income but less risk

Swarup K. S. (2003)

Empirically found that equity investors first enter capital market through investment in primary market. The main reason for slump in equity offering is lack of investor confidence in the primary market. It appeared from the analysis that the investors give importance to own analysis as compared to brokers’ advice. They also consider market price as a better indicator than analyst recommendations. Accordingly, number of suggestive measures in terms of regulatory, policy level and market oriented were suggested to improve the investor confidence in equity primary markets.

Rajeswari, T. R. and Moorthy, V. E. R. (2005)

Said that expectations of the investors influenced by their perception and human generally relate perception to action. The study revealed that the most preferred vehicle is bank deposit with mutual funds and equity on fourth and sixth respectively. The survey also revealed that the investment decision is made by investors on their own, and other sources influencing their selection decision are newspapers, magazine, brokers, television and friends or relatives.

Gupta and Naveen Jain (2008)

found that majority of the investors are from younger group and as per occupation,

salaries are more inclined towards investment. Study also argued education qualification is the major influenced factor in investment. Their most preferred investment is found to be shares followed by mutual funds. Empirically they found and argued the Indian stock market is considerably dominated by the speculating crowd, the large scale of day trading and also fact the futures trading in individual stocks is several times the value of trading in cash segment. They also found the largest proportions of the investors are worried about too much volatility of the market. For trader and speculators, price volatility is an opportunity to make quick profits. In the study, high proportions of investors have a very favorable opinion about the capital market regulation.

Objectives Of Study:

The primary objective of fund management is to manage investments on behalf of investors. Besides, some of the other objectives are as follows:

- To Ensure the highest level of safety and stability for the investors by focusing on investment opportunities that offer the right mix of risk and return.
- To Guarantee capital appreciation of the investments in the long term.
- To trace the pattern of utilization of deposits and examine the underlying profitability of funds management
- Besides long-term capital appreciation, generate regular cash flow through interest and dividend income on the investments.

Hypothesis:

- 1) Customer are not willing to invest in fund-based management (H0)
- 2) Customer are willing to invest in fund-based management(H1)

Research Methodology:

The study is based on survey technique. The study consists of analysis and Market Scoping of Financial product of IIFL. For the purpose of the study customers 100 are picked up and their views solicited on different parameters. The methodology adopted include:

- Questionnaire
- Random sample survey of customers
- Discussions with the concerned

Analysis & Interpretation Of The Data:

The study is based on survey technique. The study consists of analysis and Market coping of Financial product of IIFL. For the purpose of the study customers 100 are picked up

and their views solicited on different parameters.

OCCUPATION	% of Investors engaged in occupation	TYPES OF INVESTMENT	% of investors engaged in investment
PROFESSIONAL	16%	EQUITY FORM	44.80%
SELF EMPLOYED	16%	FIXED DEPOSIT	20.70%
EMPLOYEES	4%	DEBT MUTUALFUNDS	17.20%
STUDENTS & HOUSEWIFE	3%	NATIONAL PENSION	13.80%

Table No.1: Types Of Occupation & Types Of Investment of investors

Qualification

27 responses

Graph 1: Description about types of investment

Interpretation:

In Occupation group, out of 30 investors, 16% are professional, 16% self-employed , 4% are Employees, and 3% are others Student and house wife.44.8% investors are invest in Equity form, 20.7% investors investments in Bank fixed deposits, 17.2% investors investment in Debt Mutual funds and 13.8% investors investment in national pension system.

Out of 30 equity investors 7.4% of the investors in are Graduate/Post Graduate, 3% of investors are MBA and 3% are others.

Time period	% of investors	Type of investment more profitable	% of investors
short term	24.10%	Fixed Deposit	21.40%
medium term	20.70%	mutual Fund	57.10%
long term	21.70%	equities investment	17.90%

Table no. 2 investment based on time & profitable

Graph no. 3: Types of Investment based on time & profitability

Interpretation:

24.1% investors invest in short term of periods of investment., 20.7% investors medium term period of investment and 21.7% investors are invest in long term periods of investment. 57.1% investors feel more profit in invest in mutual funds, 21.4%investors feel more profit in fixed deposit investment, and 17.9% investors more profit in equities investment.

Interpretation:

51.9% investors have primary goals are retirement benefits for investments, 33.3% investors are goals investment for house and 11.1% investors are invest in child educations.35.7% investors are before investing in safety of principals, 25% investors consider before investing in low risk return in investment, 28.6% investors before investing considers for high return in investment and 10.7% investors are consider before invest in maturity periods.

Finding:

Equity option which is always preferable when the market is volatile. After the process tabulation and data analysis the research had explore the following finding like. According to the survey most of the customers of India Infoline says that, is it pocket friendly which is provide less investments charge than others. Lack promotions activity undertaken by India Infoline. The main purpose of investment are liquidity and returns. Investors take risk as well as get return on their investments. Commodity market are less preferred by the investors because of less awareness about commodity market. People want invest their money in securities market but they have not sufficient knowledge about investment procedures. People are not aware of hedging in stock market.

Future Scope:

There should be equal commitment for every person. There should be some promotional activity required for awareness of the customers. Provide the facility of free demonstration for all. There should be a limited number of clients under the relationship manager, so they can handle new as well as old customer properly. Improvement in the opening of De-mat account and contract notice procedure is required. Young age people

should encourage to invest in stock market.

Conclusion

On the basis of study it is found that Indian Infoline is provide better service than other stock brokers because of their timely research and personalized advice on what stocks to buy and sell, when to buy and when to sell. India Infoline provides the facility to trade as well as the relationship manager facilitate to encourage and protect the interest of the customer or the investors. It also provides the information through the internet and mobile alerts that what IPO's are coming in the market and it also provides its research on the future prospect of the IPO. It is also found that people are not aware about commodity market Hedging etc. so there should be a creation of awareness of share market and its instruments, how it takes place, when to invest or not etc. The company should come up with innovative ways of service at their door steps this may be a costly affair but will surely give positive results in the long run as the banks and insurance companies done. The company should take the initiative of training the advisors about the new funds from time to time which also makes the advisors connected to the company. The company should give emphasis on creating awareness about the market knowledge. The company should focus on the advertising strategy and also the marketing of the product.

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